

Hawking Radiation as Universal Hamiltonian, Operator and Governor of Schrodinger Equation

In Quantum Information Holography (QIH), Hawking radiation can be conceptualized as playing a multifaceted role: it is not only a transmitter of information across the cosmos but also acts as a universal Hamiltonian and operator within the quantum framework. This perspective allows us to understand how the angular frequency of Hawking radiation emitted as a Quantum State Vector (QSV) could influence and potentially govern the dynamics described by the Schrödinger equation.

Hawking Radiation as Universal Hamiltonian:

1. Hawking Radiation as an Information Carrier:

Hawking radiation, emitted from black holes, is theorized to carry information about the black hole's quantum state. This information is encoded in the radiation's quantum state vector (QSV).

2.

$$\Psi_{\text{Hawking}} = \sum_n c_n e^{-iE_n t / \hbar} |n\rangle$$

3.

Here,

4. Ψ_{Hawking} is the QSV of Hawking radiation. The coefficients c_n and energy levels E_n in the superposition represent the encoded information.

5. Hawking Radiation as the Universal Operator:

In the QIH framework, Hawking radiation can be seen as a universal operator that influences the quantum state of each qubit in the Planck qubit lattice.

$$\hat{H}^{\text{Hawking}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \hbar \omega_i \hat{O}^i$$

$\hat{H}^{\text{Hawking}}$ represents the Hawking radiation as an operator, where ω_i are the angular frequencies, and $\hat{O}^i$ are operators acting on each qubit.

Influence on Schrödinger Equation:

1. Hawking Radiation Governing Quantum Dynamics:

The Schrödinger equation, describing the time evolution of a quantum system, could be governed by the Hawking radiation through its role as the universal Hamiltonian.

$$i\hbar \partial_t |\Psi(t)\rangle = \hat{H}^{\text{Hawking}} |\Psi(t)\rangle$$

In this formulation, the Hawking radiation's influence is embedded in the evolution of the quantum state $|\Psi(t)\rangle$.

2. Angular Frequency's Role:

The angular frequency of Hawking radiation, ω , is crucial in determining the energy transitions and thus the dynamics of the quantum states in the system.

$$\omega_n = \hbar E_n$$

This relationship establishes a direct connection between the energy levels of the quantum states and the angular frequency of the Hawking radiation.

Conclusion:

In the realm of QIH, Hawking radiation emerges as a pivotal element, acting simultaneously as an information carrier, a universal Hamiltonian, and an operator. This conceptualization allows for a deeper understanding of quantum dynamics, where the angular frequency of Hawking radiation influences the time evolution of quantum states as described by the Schrödinger equation. Such a framework integrates the principles of holography, quantum information, and traditional quantum mechanics, offering a novel approach to understanding the intricate interplay between black holes, Hawking radiation, and the fundamental nature of quantum spacetime.